

ANALYSIS OF IDIOMS INVOLVING CLOTHES NAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

¹S.M.Qurbonova

The doctor of philosophy in philological sciences

²Xujanazarova Umida

The master's degree student of Fergana state university

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7947427>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th May 2023

Accepted: 17th May 2023

Online: 18th May 2023

KEY WORDS

Multi - word expressions, idiomatic expressions, phrase, idiom, to'n, do'ppi, yeng.

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the essence of figures of speech, its understanding with idioms and phrases as local and historical traditions among people.

Speaking with colorful words that describe our feelings better makes our speech more effective. For instance, it is largely known that we use some multi-word expressions, such as idioms and phrases to express many concepts. These expressions must be learned alongside the words and rules that enable us to compare between languages. In this article, we are going to analyze clothing idioms in English and Uzbek.

Idioms are an expression in the usage of a language that is peculiar to itself either in having a meaning that cannot be derived from the conjoined meanings of its elements. Categorized as formulaic language, an idiom's figurative meaning is different from the literal meaning. Idioms occur frequently in all languages, in English alone there are an estimated twenty-five million idiomatic expressions. In linguistics, idioms are usually presumed to be figures of speech contradicting the principle of compositionality. That compositionality is the key notion for the analysis of idioms is emphasized in most accounts of idioms. This principle states that the meaning of a whole should be constructed from the meanings of the parts that make up the whole. In other words, one should be in a position to understand the whole if one understands the meanings of each of the parts that make up the whole. The following example is widely employed to illustrate the point:

It's almost exam time, so Fred need to **roll up his sleeves** this weekend.

Understood compositionally, has literally rolled his sleeves. The much more likely idiomatic reading, however, is non-compositional: Fred is understood to work hard. Arriving at the idiomatic reading from the literal reading is unlikely for most speakers. What this means is that the idiomatic reading is, rather, stored as a single lexical item that is now largely independent of the literal reading.

A word-by-word translation of an opaque idiom will most likely not convey the same meaning in other languages. However if we translate this idiom into the Uzbek language word-by-word, we can gain the meaning: "Yeng shimarmoq". In the Uzbek language it also

represents clothing idiom and it means: “to try to do something”. Here we have some other idioms that express clothing names:

1) Kid gloves

Meaning: If you treat someone with kid gloves, you deal with them very gently or carefully. The term comes from gloves made from the leather of a young animal, in this case the goat, which are very soft and not meant for hard work.

Example: A social worker complained that some parents treat their teenage children with kid gloves, and they end up acting like spoiled brats.

2) Walk a mile in someone’s shoes

Meaning: you should try to understand someone before criticising them. The full idiom is: Before you judge someone, walk a mile in their shoes.

Example: My brother can come across as selfish or mean-spirited, but you should try walking a mile in his shoes before criticising him; he was bullied a lot in school.

3) Tighten your belt

Meaning: to spend less money than you did before

Example: With the economy so bad and thousands of people losing their jobs, we all have to tighten our belts.

In the Uzbek language there are many idioms related to clothing names. For example:

1) “Bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmoq”

Meaning: to be united, to be unanimous

Example : Ko’pchilik bir yoqadan bosh chiqarib harakat qilsa, uning kuchi okean to’lqinidan ham zo’r bo’ladi.

2) “To’nini teskari kiyib oldi”

Meaning: to be obstinate without turning off

Example: Bu sovuq gap tufayli tuyqusdan u to’nini teskari kiydi.

3) Do’ppisini osmonga otdi

Ma’nosi: juda hursand bo’ldi

Misol: Agar bugun men 5 baho olsam, judayam do’ppimni osmonga otaman.

In summary, it should be said that it has become an integral part of people’s lives due to the broad scope of the subject of phrases and proverbs, they are social from the most complex problems of life to the smallest of family life to their habits, from high moral standards to small human flaws, from the philosophical outlook to the characteristics of the smallest animals found his vision. Proverbs and expressions are life observations of our people and based on his experiences, his wisdom, lifestyle, behavior passed from centuries to centuries as a spiritual treasure expressing its culture. Such words and phrases used in the proverbs have absorbed the nationality of the people for centuries and without any explanation it is shown as a means of showing the national mentality.

References:

1. Amosova N.N. Fundamentals of English phraseology. L., 1963.208 p.
2. Foal T.V. Dictionary of linguistic terms. Ed. 5th, Nazran, 2010. 486 p.
3. Kunin A.V. Phraseology course of modern English. 2nd ed. Revised. M., 1996.381 p.
4. Smirnitsky A.I. Lexicology of the English language. M.: Foreign literature, 1956. 260 p.

5. Vinogradov V.V. Selected Works.Lexicology and lexicography.M., 1977.312 p.
6. Sh. Rahmatullayev. "O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati". T.1978
7. KIYIM-KECHAK REALIYA ISHTIROKIDAGI MATN PERSEPSIYASI Adiba Matlubovna Yusupova. O'zMU. November,2020